

PSCCTEM Ontology to overcome pesticide paradox in Model Based Testing

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Abstract—This research proposed ontologies to retain information and knowledge for overcoming pesticide paradox in model based testing. Domain ontology was constructed, which described the vocabularies related to a software engineering domain. The ontology retained the structure of a Polymorphism State Collaboration Class Test Model (PSCCTEM) by defining the test model's structural elements and the relationships between them. In this research, the rules for transforming UML PSCCTEM test model into behavioral model ontology, proposed based on the Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM). The proposed solution argued that developing a new testing phase that help the user to regenerate the test steps easily according to system modifications that will overcome pesticide paradox.

Keywords

Ontologies; pesticide paradox; software engineering; Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM).

i. Introduction

Software testing is an attempt to execute a program with well-designed input data to discover failures. In other words, "Testing is the process of drying out a program with the intent of uncovering errors". Testing identifies faults, whose removal enhancing the software quality by increasing the software's reliability [1]. Basically, the testing procedure consists of three phases: (i) Test Case Creation, (ii) Test Case Execution and (iii) Test Case Evaluation. Test case creation process represents a vital phase among the three phases [2]. Singh (2013) stated seven principles of testing which must be regarded while testing a product. The last principle is the pesticide paradox states that, if similar set of test cases are used repeatedly then chances of forecasting defects can be reduced. Therefore, users have to update and check their test cases on continual basis [3]. In model-based testing, test cases are derived from a model representing software behavior. In this approach, the System under Test (SUT) is converted into System Test Graph (STG); the graph is traversed to generate test cases automatically based on coverage criteria and a fault model [4]. The literature review shows that (1) the existing approaches on model-based testing using UML Diagrams tend to rely on intermediate formats and formalisms for model verification and test generation. (2) A multitude of graph-based coverage criteria, and use graph search algorithms employed. (3) Most approaches target very restricted application domains, and (4) there is currently a clear lack of holistic approaches for model-based testing using UML diagrams. Most of the well-known model based testing techniques for test case generation encounter pesticide paradox. To overcome such limitations, new approaches and solutions need to be proposed. This research presents the testing procedure that can be enhanced by

developing a new ontology testing phase to retain software testing model. This may help the user to regenerate the steps easily to improve the reusability and modifiability of testing methods, and suite to overcome pesticide paradox. The rest of this paper organized as follows: Section 2 provides a brief background on the model based testing and also highlights related work. Section 3 presents the proposed test model that capture complete picture of the system. Section 4 presents the transformation rules used to build the ontology. Section 5 presents case study. Finally, Section 6 concludes the paper and outlines future work.

ii. BACKGROUND AND RELATED WORK

A considerable amount of work targets the generation of test inputs, the selection of test scenarios, and the generation of test oracles from formal models and specification. Arvinder Kaur et al (2018) presented an approach to generate test cases automatically from collaboration diagrams and validation of results using mutation testing. The approach proposed an algorithm for generation of graphs from collaboration diagrams ensuring full path coverage. The results generated after traversal of graph covered all the valid, invalid and terminated paths but still restricts the path selection to minimal and avoid duplicate or unbounded path selection [5]. WeifengXu et al (2016) Proposed an integration testing approach based on the core concept of contracts (i.e., preconditions and postconditions of components calls in first-order logic) to exercise component interactions. They converted the test model into operational model for correctness analysis and generation of coverage-based tests (including state coverage, transition or component coverage, and reachability coverage) of a contract-based test model. They executed their approach in framework that generates the test cases for large collection of programming languages. To measure the effectiveness of their approach, they executed experiments to check the performance and fault detection capabilities of tests [6]. In [7], Yi Sun et al (2017) proposed an approach for integration test cases generation based on collaboration diagram and logic contracts to automatically generate integration test cases. The researchers tried to overcome the shortcoming exist in [6] by extracting control flow information from collaboration diagram and combining with contracts as component specification. An intermediate model called execution tree of components is established, and then test cases are automatically generated through contract solving technology. Muhammad Nouman Zafar et al (2021) proposed GraphWalker model based test framework to generate test scripts for embedded software controlling. The GraphWalker

defines mapping rules for converting abstract test cases to executable test cases [8]. Qiu Zhipeng et al (2021) proposed formal requirement model (VRM) to generate test cases by exploring the input and output structure of the model [9].

Few researches have studied in the direction of developing ontologies to improve software testing phase. Josip Bozic et al (2021) proposed ontologies based web testing approach that combines knowledge about common attacks and the system under test. The proposed approach depends on transforms ontologies into input models and using a combinatorial testing algorithm for deducing the test cases [11]. Anjalika and et al (2017) introduced test case extraction based on ontology reasoning. For this goal, requirement ontology is first constructed to store requirement knowledge; test cases are derived from requirement based on action, object and actor. Actions related to objects and actors that are responsible for actions are traversed to extract data properties [12]. Likewise, Valeh H. Nasser and et al (2010) proposed an approach for unit test case generation from knowledge base artifact in the form of ontologies. The test oracle considered is a UML state machine, also called a state-chart, which is a design-level abstraction of a unit's behavior. The proposed approach enables generation of required test cases based on the pre-defined coverage criteria [13]. Although, the new exist testing methods are applicable to generate test cases from a formal model and specification, the literature review shows that research is lacking in overcoming pesticide paradox. No specific study focused on developing dynamic test case generation approach based on ontology to capture complete picture of the system.

iii. The proposed Framework of Test Model

The proposed test model uses usecase diagram, collaboration diagram, class diagram, and statechart diagrams to test classes' interactions for a specific use case of all possible object states. Figure (1) shows the framework of the general procedure to create the test model. Before the test model construction, it is assumed that all UML diagrams are consistent. In previous work, the augmentation of collaboration diagram with objects states to develop the SCCTEM (State Collaboration Class Test Model) was already done that can be used to uncover state-dependent interaction faults, e.g., inconsistent states of classes involved in a collaboration diagram, wrong calling state of a class in a collaboration diagram, and wrong initial state of a class in a collaboration diagram [14]. After the SCCTEM has been generated, this research proposes calling of class diagram of the system to capture inheritance relations and polymorphic methods for complete and coherent description of the system. Polymorphic classes are extracted from class diagram according to the objects involved in collaboration graph. The extracted polymorphic information is added into SCCTEM to create the UML based Polymorphism State Collaboration Class Test Model (PSCCTEM).

iv. Transformation of UML PSCCTEM Test Model into Behavioral Model Ontology

A domain ontology will be constructed, which Describes the vocabulary related to an applied domain (for example, information systems or medicine), by means of the specialization of the introduced concepts of high-level ontologies [15]. The ontology retains the structure of a PSCCTEM test model by defining the test model's constructs and the relationships between them. Behavioral model ontology for PSCCTEM test model is built and saved in RDF/XML file format to extract test cases according to defined coverage criteria. The conceptual modeling of the UML test model is likely to reflect the complete picture of the system. Thus, the ontology structure (concepts and properties) can be defined and

fixed by human who studied the domain knowledge of UML models.

Fig .1. Framework for Proposed Test Model Generation.

Contrariwise, the ontology instantiation will vary depending on requirement descriptions. In this section, the rules for transforming UML PSCCTEM test model into behavioral model ontology proposed based on the Ontology Definition Metamodel (ODM), adopted by the OMG [16]. The notion for mapping between UML and OWL must be formalized. The proposed notation shown as follows:

- In the UML, the class is represented as U(C), the attribute is represented as U(A), and the relation is represented as U(R).
- In OWL the class is represented as O(C), data type property is represented as O(A), and object property between classes is represented as O(E1OE2).

In the following section, the proposed conversion rules are introduced in details.

a. Transformation of Root Component

Root component in the PSCCTEM test model is null node for starting the interaction. The concept of class exists in both UML and OWL2. In UML, The class structures the same properties, methods, and relationships for a set of objects. Class properties set the structure of the class and methods of the class determine the behavior of the instances of the class. In OWL2, Class in is an empty structure or has multiple individuals and do not manipulate operations on those individuals [16]. So, the transformation rule for Root component in UML to Root component in OWL ontology as follows:

PSCCTEM Rule 1: the Root component in PSCCTEM test model is null vertex for starting the interaction. In Behavioral Model Ontology (BMO), it is transformed into empty Root class respectively for starting the interaction.

b. Transformation of Class Component

PSCCTEM Rule 2: each PSCCTEM class U(C) is transformed into class O(C) respectively in Behavioral Model Ontology based on OWL2, set Disjoint Classes properties for each class if they are not generalization.

c. Transformation of Abstract Class Component

The abstract Class component represents the class which has the inheritance relationship and polymorphic methods. for example, the "Payment" class is a parent class of the "Credit Card" and "PayPal" classes, so that the "Credit Card" and "PayPal" classes inherit "check Out()" methods from the "Payment" class. In UML, this is known as generalization relationship between the base class "Payment" and the sub classes "Credit Card" and "PayPal". The

generalization indicates to the existence of the child classes that inherit from the base class. In UML and OWL, generalization and specialization concepts are defined. In OWL, The existence of inheritance leads to the transforming of a base class into associated with child class component with corresponding constraint. The base generalization transformation rule from UML into OWL as follow:

PSCCTEM Rule 3: In PSCCTEM test model, the generalization and association between the U(C) and the subclass U(C_i), do the following: Add the abstract class O(A_C) and class O(C_i) which is child class of class O(C).

d. Transformation of the Class Attributes

In UML, The Properties of the class must be unparalleled in the context of the class. Attributes are defined to capture real world, and to be accessible from other classes. In the PSCCTEM test model, the attributes are used to describe the content of each class within the test path. The class- name identifies the name of the class. The message attributes show the message name and number. The state shows every state within the class. The State _Transition shows every state transition which is triggered by the received message. In OWL, the retrieval access does not supported in the data type properties. So, the transformation rule of attributes in UML into Behavioral Model ontology depends on the type of the attribute. The attribute of primitive data type is transformed into a data type property in the OWL ontology. The attribute of the type class is transformed into an object property

o *Transformation of the Message Details*

The attributes of the interaction between classes as the number, operation (iteration or condition), and name of the message need to be stored as a simple attributes in the message association class that enables to retrieve them for building test paths. In the following, the transformation rule for mapping message attributes from UML based test model to model behavior Ontology:-

PSCCTEM Rule 4.1: In PSCCTEM test model that Considering the Message details as simple attributes, for each simple Attribute in test model class, Transformation of attribute U(att M)of class U(C)that the data type is primitive data type , create a data type property by respectively associating with its domain and range the URI of the class corresponding to the attribute and the XSD type corresponding to the type of the attribute in the UML test model diagram.

o *Transformation of the State and State Transition Attributes*

Each test path may go through the modal class, the non- modal class or the abstract class. Each state transition path of the modal class is from a source state to a destination state of state transition when it receives a particular message. The captured states and state transitions of the model classes in PSCCTEM test model will need transformation rules for mapping them into OWL Ontology. This research proposes to treat states and state transitions of each model class as separate classes and connect them with the base model class through "Object Property" axiom. The research did this assumption because each model class may have one or more state and not all classes are model classes. Also, these states are not the attributes of the classes (methods of model classes). So, they will be stored in separate classes and access them through associations. The transformation rule for the states and state transitions of the model class in PSCCTEM test model show in the following:

PSCCTEM Rule 4.2: In PSCCTEM test model ontology that considering the state and state transition of the model class as class and make Association between model class and state, state transition class through object property with domain is O (M_C), range is O (State).

e. Transformation of the Relation Between Classes

The test case starts with dummy node and builds by the ascending order of the entire messages in the UML PSCCTEM model. The total number of test paths is decided by the number of state

transition paths of the modal class and the number of Childs classes of abstract classes. In this section, the transformation rules for mapping interactions among objects in the PSCCTEM test model into behavior ontology model is described. In previous sections, the message details are transformed in OWL Ontology as attributes of the message Association class using data type property. But, the sender and receiver of the message must be retained in the ontology to be able to retrieve the message expression for building test paths. Message links in PSCCTEM test model is type of class association relation. In UML, the association can be one-directional or uni-directional. In OWL, association between classes can be transformed into an object property. For uni-directional association, each direction is converted into object property. Then, the transformation rule for mapping class association links from UML based test model to OWL Ontology as follow:-

PSCCTEM Rule 5: In PSCCTEM test model that Considering the Message link as association class with attributes, the transformation rules for association class M₀ between classes O₁ and O₂ is formally transformed to:

- An OWL class (named message association class) with message association class instance for each message, and two pairs of inverse object properties for every class connected to the association class.
- Chains of Object properties between classes connected to the message association class, the semantics of the classes and properties of this ontology are described in Table 1 and Table 2.

Table I.Semantics of PSCCTEM Ontology Classes.

Class	Description
Root Class	A PSCCTEM class to initialize the interaction.
Sender Class	Base class contains classes that send messages
Receiver Class	Base class contains classes that receive messages
Model Class	A model class is class that has states
Non model class	Non model class is a class that don't have states
Abstract class	The Abstract Class represents the class which has the inheritance relationship and polymorphic methods.
State class	State class represents states of the model class.
Transition class	A Transition class represents state transitions of the model class.

Table II.Semantics of properties of PSCCTEM ontology

Property	Domain	Range	Description
Send Message	Sender Class	Message Association Class	It is a collection that contains the sent messages of the PSCCTEM.
Receive Message	Message Association Class	Receiver Class	It is a collection that contains the received messages of the PSCCTEM.
Has States	Model class	State class of model class	It is a collection that contains the states of the model class.
Has Transitions	Model class	Transition class of	It is a collection that contains the transitions of the

		model class	model class.
From	Transition	State	It is a state, which is the source of the transition.
To	Transition	State	It is a state, which is the destination of the transition.

o PSCCTEM Test Model Generation

As shown in figure (3), PSCCTEM Test model for medical online shopping portal is generated based on system scenario. A medical online shopping portal allows their customers to register to their portal. The customer uses the system to find medical equipment (ex. a defibrillators, Anesthesia Machines, Patient Monitors, Sterilizers, Surgical Tables or Blanket and Fluid Warmers). He can login to the system anytime to search for the items. The customer can edit the final cart then submit the final cart for check out and make a payment. The site's administrator can update different items in the system; manage the registration of new customer. After payment a receipt will be sent to customer in hard or soft copy. The shipment data will be entered to deliver the order. The SCCTEM of the Medical Online Shopping Portal is generated from collaboration graph and statechart diagrams. Then, inheritance information of the corresponding classes in the SCCTEM model is extracted from class diagram to be used in creating PSCCTEM test model. In this step the SCCTEM is augmented with inheritance and polymorphic information captured from class diagram. The rectangle of the compound dotted line represents the polymorphic relationship in the class diagram.

v. Case Study

It is not accurate to apply the approach to one system to validate it. So, two case studies are implemented for approach validation. In this section evaluation of the approach is demonstrated as follow: -
First : Is building test model for the system.
Second: Is building behavioral model ontology for the system.

a. PSCCTEM Ontology Generation for Medical Online Shopping Portal

Fig .3. PSCCTEM Diagram for medical Online shopping Portal.

o Behavioral Model Ontology for Medical Online Shopping Portal

Ontology is developed using web interface of Protégé. Medical PSCCTEM Ontology can be defined as classes, subclasses; Relationship between classes implemented using data and object properties as depicted in Figure (4).

Fig.4. Object Properties, Data Properties.

To validate the semantic consistency of the generated ontology, graphical representation of the medical portal ontology obtained using the plugin OntoGraf protégé to show the hierarchy of the test model. As shown in figure(4), there is object property called send message, the domain of the property is sender class, and the range of the property is message association class. Another object property is receive message, the domain of the property is message association class and the range is receiver class. Also, there is object property with name has state between receiver class and state class, the domain of the property is receiver class, and the range is state class. Finally, there are two object properties with name from and to between state class and state transition class to represent the source and destination states of state transition. Also, in the figure there is individual of message association class called update product message with two object properties; send message and receive message. The domain of the send message object property is the instance of the portal'sAdmin class as sender class and the range of the receive message is the

Behavioral Model Ontology for Library Management System

Based on a set of transformation rules for mapping between UML test model and OWL ontology, Behavioral model ontology for PSCOTEM test model is generated and saved in RDF/XML file format. According to PSCCTEM ontology for library management system graphical representation of the ontology is extracted, as depicted in Figure (7).

Fig .5. Graphical Representation of Medical Online Shopping Portal Ontology.

Fig .7. Graphical Representation of Library Management System Ontology.

Based on the graphical representation of the ontologies, the generated ontologies completely represent the constructs of PSCCTEM test model, without any error. Therefore, it is dependable to generate test cases to overcome pesticide paradox. A dynamic approach can be developed to generate test cases to overcome pesticide paradox.

vi. CONCLUSION

In this research, a new approach to overcome pesticide paradox in model based testing is presented. This study focused on developing dynamic test case generation based on ontology building. The PSCCTEM ontology is developed using Web Ontology Language (OWL) to map system specifications into OWL specification. The conceptual modeling of the UML test model is likely to reflect the complete picture of the system. Thus, the ontology structure (concepts and properties) can be defined and fixed by human study of the domain knowledge of UML models. Contrariwise, the ontology instantiation will vary depending on requirement descriptions. A limitation of mapping approach is that it does not implement algorithm to manipulate RDF/XML file to generate test cases. The future research will be focused on developing tool that captures the constructs of PSCCTEM test model and generate a set of algorithms to generate test suite.

vii. References

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Fig .6. PSCCTEM Diagram for Library Management System.

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